

11 PRM for plant regeneration, which was calculated as number of calli producing green plants relative to total calli plated.

Genotype and medium interaction showed significant effect on callus induction (Table 2). All genotypes responded with callus induction being genotype- and medium-dependent. Callus induction ranged from 1.8% in IR64/IR2588-1-3-2 on G1 medium to 27.9% in Nep Hoa Vang on L8 medium. Among the three CIM tested, L8 gave the highest average callus induction of 19.5%, followed by G1 and Fj.

Green plant production ranged from 13.3% in IR64/IR2588-1-3-2 to 25.4% in IR8/828//Nep Ga Gay (Table 2). Significant effects of the interactions among genotypes, CIM, and PRM were observed. Among the PRM used, however, M6 medium (Murashige and

Table 2. Interaction between genotype and medium on callus induction and plant regeneration of Indica rices.

Genotype	Callus induction ^a (%)			Green plant regeneration ^b (%)	
	Fj	G1	L8		
C15/Nep Hoa Vang (F ₁)	4.8	efghijk	13.0 cd	15.6 c	17.7 cd
C15/Nep Ga Gay (F ₁)	5.5	defghi	15.2 bc	15.4 c	15.1 de
IR1529-680-3-2/Pelita (line)	7.0	cde	19.4 ab	25.4 ab	13.3 f
IR8/DU//IR529 (line)	4.9	efghijk	16.8 abc	22.5 b	17.9 cd
IR8/828//Nep Ga Gay (line)	3.8	hijklmn	5.6 f	17.1 c	25.4 a
IR8/DU//C4-63///IR1569 (line)	5.2	defghi	18.9 ab	22.1 b	18.0 c
184/IR8 (line)	3.7	hijklmn	6.8 ef	11.4 d	21.7 b
IR64/IR2588-1-3-2 (line)	2.7	mno	1.8 g	16.4 c	13.3 f
C10 (variety)	5.7	cdefgh	16.7 abc	11.2 d	16.3 cd
Xuan So 4 (variety)	13.2 a		19.5 a	24.1 ab	23.0 ab
Nep Hoa Vang (variety)	7.8 bc		18.7 ab	27.9 a	14.9 ef
Nep Ga Gay (variety)	4.6	fghijkl	13.3 cd	24.6 ab	17.5 cd

^aMeans in a column with the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. Means among CIM in a row are separated using LSD_{0.05} = 2.59. ^bThe response for each variety is the mean of 11 PRM.

Skoog basal supplemented with 1.0 mg naphthalene acetic acid/liter and 8 mg kinetin/liter) produced the most green

plants. A total of 3211 green plants were regenerated from these materials; 40% of the regenerants produced seeds. ■

Yield potential

Different grades of grain occur during grain filling in short- and medium-duration rice

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We graded grain during grain filling in five rice cultivars in 1991 kharif (monsoon) season at IARI. Panicles emerging synchronously from the main tillers were labeled. Five panicles per cultivar were collected at a 5-d interval from 15 to 35 d after panicle emergence (DAPE). Panicles were threshed and graded by specific gravity method.

Good and high density grains (HDG) constituted 67% of total grains in Rasi at 15 DAPE (see table). This percentage increased towards maturity, although at 25 DAPE it nearly stabilized at 77% of the total grains/panicle. Unfilled grains constituted 16% of the total as early as 15 DAPE and declined gradually towards maturity.

In Pusa 2-21, HDG made up about 55% of the total grains at 15 DAPE; this percentage remained almost stable until maturity.

Pusa 743 has good grain type. The occurrence of good grains/panicle was almost stable around 20 DAPE, although at 15 DAPE, good grade grains were only 8.8% of the total. HDG/panicle was 9.2% at 20 DAPE, dropped, and then climbed to 10% at 35 DAPE.

In Pusa 169, unfilled grains coupled with poor and average grain accounted for 90% of total grains at 15 DAPE, but dropped to 71% at maturity.

Good plus HDG grains made up 46% of total grains/panicle at 15 DAPE in Jaya and 65% at 30 DAPE. The appearance of this high percentage of good plus HDG at 15 DAPE indicates that this is a genotypic character distinct from large grain size and high total grains/panicle.

Many HDG appeared as early as 15 DAPE in short-duration cultivars such as Rasi and Pusa 2-21. HDG was barely evident up to 30 DAPE in medium-duration cultivars, such as Pusa 169 and Pusa 743. These results suggest that grain filling may be a predetermined phenomenon or a genotypic character. ■

Number and percentage of different grades of grain/panicle at successive growth stages during grain filling. IARI, New Delhi, India, 1991 kharif.

Cultivar	DAPE ^a	High density grains/panicle		Good grains/panicle		Av grains/panicle		Poor grains/panicle		Unfilled grains/panicle		Total grains/panicle (no.)
		no.	% ^b	no.	%	no.	%	no.	%	no.	%	
Rasi	15	80	(58.4)	12	(8.8)	8	(5.8)	16	(11.4)	21	(15.6)	137
	20	96	(62.3)	12	(7.8)	8	(5.2)	16	(10.4)	22	(14.3)	154
	25	91	(64.5)	18	(12.8)	7	(5.0)	8	(5.7)	17	(12.0)	141
	30	59	(48.8)	43	(35.5)	4	(3.3)	4	(3.3)	11	(9.1)	121
	35	104	(61.9)	31	(18.5)	7	(4.2)	11	(6.5)	15	(8.9)	168

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Cultivar	DAPE ^a	High density grains/ panicle		Good grains/ panicle		Av grains/ panicle		Poor grains/ panicle		Unfilled grains/ panicle		Total grains/ panicle (no.)
		no.	% ^b	no.	%	no.	%	no.	%	no.	%	
Pusa 2-21	15	83	(55.2)	2	(1.3)	4	(2.7)	10	(6.9)	51	(33.9)	150
	20	105	(59.3)	4	(2.3)	4	(2.7)	32	(18.2)	32	(18.1)	177
	25	94	(59.9)	16	(10.2)	12	(7.6)	26	(16.6)	9	(5.8)	157
	30	73	(50.0)	13	(8.9)	11	(7.5)	35	(24.0)	14	(9.6)	146
	35	81	(51.3)	30	(19.0)	15	(9.5)	25	(15.8)	7	(4.4)	158
Pusa 743	15	0.3	(0.2)	15	(8.8)	35	(20.6)	48	(28.2)	72	(42.3)	170
	20	14	(9.2)	78	(51.3)	7	(4.6)	24	(15.8)	29	(19.1)	152
	25	2	(1.3)	74	(47.1)	38	(24.2)	18	(11.5)	25	(15.9)	157
	30	2	(1.4)	72	(50.7)	3	(19.1)	9	(6.3)	32	(22.5)	142
	35	13	(10.0)	59	(45.7)	17	(13.2)	15	(11.6)	25	(19.4)	129
Pusa 169	15	0.3	(0.2)	19	(10.3)	32	(17.4)	40	(21.7)	93	(50.5)	184
	20	2	(1.2)	50	(30.7)	12	(7.4)	15	(9.2)	84	(51.5)	163
	25	1	(0.5)	27	(14.4)	46	(24.5)	27	(14.4)	87	(46.3)	188
	30	1	(0.7)	25	(17.6)	45	(31.7)	25	(17.6)	46	(32.4)	142
	35	7	(3.6)	50	(25.4)	30	(15.2)	46	(23.4)	64	(32.5)	197
Jaya	15	12	(7.2)	65	(39.2)	22	(13.3)	18	(10.8)	49	(29.5)	166
	20	16	(8.7)	73	(39.4)	27	(14.8)	21	(11.5)	46	(25.1)	183
	25	34	(17.7)	85	(44.3)	16	(8.3)	27	(14.0)	30	(15.6)	192
	30	33	(18.6)	82	(46.3)	17	(9.6)	33	(18.6)	12	(6.8)	177
	35	41	(22.0)	76	(40.9)	16	(8.6)	33	(17.7)	20	(10.8)	186

^aDAPE = d after panicle emergence. ^bNumbers in parentheses indicate percentage of total grains/panicle.

Pest resistance—diseases

Using pedigree analysis to identify sources of resistance to rice hoja blanca virus (RHBV)

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RHBV is the only virus disease of rice in the western hemisphere. It is restricted to Latin America. The insect *Tagosodes orizicolus* (Muir) transmits RHBV. To identify the original sources of resistance, we searched the literature for varieties and lines reported as resistant or moderately resistant to RHBV and conducted pedigree analyses.

Cultivars reported to have some degree of resistance, their parents with unknown reaction, and some landraces contributing to the pedigrees were evaluated in the greenhouse for their

reaction to RHBV. Cages (2 × 1 × 1 m) with capacity for 180 pots, each containing 10 plants, were used. Ten pots with 15-d-old plants of each genotype were randomly distributed within the cage and exposed for 5 d to a colony of the insect vector with at least 70% of the individuals carrying the virus. Each plant was assessed for disease symptoms 15 d after exposure.

Eight of the nine varieties or lines previously reported as resistant to RHBV showed infections of less than 30%, which is the accepted resistance level (see table). The susceptible reaction of line IR1721-146-4-3 was reconfirmed by the performance of its parents, *Oryza nivara* and IR24, and its other ancestors, B5580A1-15 and Sigadis (parents of IR127, used to develop IR24), suggesting the lack of genetic sources of resistance.

One accession of Agostano and Balilla and both of Blue Rose and Takao Iku 18 showed a reaction similar to that of the resistant check. It can be inferred that

Colombia 1 carries the resistance genes of Takao Iku 18 because its other parent, Napal, was reported as susceptible when released. Genes of Agostano (and possibly Balilla and Blue Rose) could be responsible for the resistance of Diamante, and ICA10 could be a source of the resistance genes coming from PI215936. Lacrosse's pedigree analysis showed that its ancestors were Colusa, Blue Rose, Shoemed, and Fortuna; the observed resistance could come from the first two varieties. Doing the same exercise with the *Oryzica* varieties, Takao Iku 18 appears to be the most probable source of resistance. For Llanos 4, Taichung 65 and Makalioka might have contributed resistance genes through IRAT122 (Chianan 8/Makalioka).

Pedigree analysis can be used to identify major sources of resistance and to help select parents that enable diverse genes to be incorporated into a breeding program. Pedigree analysis reduces the crosses needed to determine the relationship among the resistance sources identified. ■